

Five-coordinate Complexes of Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with a Pyrazole-derived Macrocycle

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The synthesis and physicochemical characterisation of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of a pyrazole-derived macrocycle, viz. acetylacetonone bis-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5) carbohydrazone, AcH(MPCH), are reported. The complex species [MAc(MPCH) X]. (M=Ni/Cu X=a counterion like Cl, Br, NO₃, ClO₄, etc.) formed by a template methodology, have been characterised through molar conductances, magnetic and esr electronic and vibrational spectral parameters. Magnetic and spectral features classify the reported complexes as five-coordinate square-pyramidal species. It is pointed out that the open-chain tetradentate macrocyclic ligand AcH(MPCH), formed in situ, coordinates through two pyrazolyl (ring) nitrogens ('N) and two azomethine (C=N) nitrogens with the counterion (X) being bonded to the central Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ion. The esr data on the polycrystalline forms of Cu^{II} species indicate a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state and the g_{av} values are also commensurate with the proposed five-coordinate geometry of Cu^{II} species.

The well-documented antituberculous activity of isonicotinyl acid hydrazide (Isoniazid) has been attributed to some sort of chelation phenomenon with trace transition metal ions in the living systems¹. This has inspired a substantial amount of research on the coordination behaviour of N-heterocyclic acid hydrazides and their derivatives²⁻⁶. In a separate approach, the significant importance of the coordination chemistry of pyrazole-derivatives, primarily because of bioimplications of the free ligands, has been well authenticated by a recent review article by Trofimenko⁷ which also refers remarkable work from our laboratory. In continuation of our earlier reports^{4,5} on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases of pyrazolyl acid hydrazides, the present communication

is concerned with the synthesis and physicochemical characterisation of host of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, formed by a template methodology, with a pyrazole-derived macrocycle, viz. acetylacetonone bis-methylpyrazolyl carbohydrazone, AcH(MPCH)₂.

Results and Discussion

A template methodology by interaction of the reactants, viz. acetylacetonone (AcAcH), 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazone (MPCH) in presence of M(II) salts in appropriate proportion has yielded the reported complex species of the general composition, [MAc(MPCH)₂X] (M=Ni/Cu, X=a counterion like Cl, Br, etc.) as shown by C, H, N analyses (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Yield %	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)				Anion (X)	μ_{eff} B.M.	Δ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	C	H	N			
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ Cl	30	13.26 (13.42)	41.00 (41.17)	4.41 (4.57)	25.20 (25.62)	8.23 (8.12)	2.18	126
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ Br	35	12.28 (12.18)	37.09 (37.37)	4.08 (4.15)	23.00 (23.25)	16.45 (16.60)	2.45	53
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ (NO ₃)	30	12.45 (12.65)	38.70 (38.82)	4.20 (4.31)	27.38 (27.17) ^a	—	3.00	45
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ (SCN)	40	12.61 (12.77)	39.01 (40.76)	4.31 (4.35)	27.26 (27.40)	6.63 (6.96) ^b	3.05	110
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ (ClO ₄)	40	11.55 (11.71)	35.78 (35.91)	3.97 (3.99)	22.42 (22.34)	7.19 (7.08) ^c	3.07	120
NiAc(MPCH) ₂ (BF ₄)	38	11.98 (12.06)	36.73 (36.98)	4.02 (4.11)	23.00 (23.01)	—	2.13	51
CuAc(MPCH) ₂ Cl	25	14.33 (14.63)	40.48 (40.72)	4.42 (4.52)	25.21 (25.34)	8.25 (8.03)	2.20	35
CuAc(MPCH) ₂ Br	23	13.21 (13.05)	36.87 (36.99)	4.05 (4.11)	22.87 (23.02)	16.26 (16.44)	1.58	31
CuAc(MPCH) ₂ (NO ₃)	20	13.46 (13.55)	38.26 (38.42)	4.22 (4.27)	26.67 (26.89) ^a	—	1.15	30
CuAc(MPCH) ₂ (ClO ₄)	22	12.44 (12.55)	35.40 (35.57)	3.78 (3.95)	22.05 (22.13)	7.26 (7.01) ^d	1.56	96

*At 303 K. ** 1.0×10^{-3} M solution in DMF. ^aIncluding nitrogen present in nitrate. ^bPercentage of sulphur. ^cPercentage of chlorine present in perchlorate. ^dIncluding nitrogen present in thiocyanate.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Ni^{II} complexes, NiAc(MPCH)₂X, lie in the range 2.18–3.13 B.M. Although magnetic moments of nickel(II) chloride (2.18 B.M.) and nickel(II) bromide (2.45 B.M.) complexes are comparatively much lower⁸ and values as low as 2.50 B.M. are reported in literature⁹, the μ_B values, in general, are well within the range known for five-coordinate Ni^{II} complexes. The lowering in μ_B may be ascribed to a distortion of the molecule from idealised symmetry. The molar conductance values in DMF (50–120 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) (Table 1) indicate the ionic nature of the nickel(II) species showing their 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour of the complexes at least in solution of the said solvent¹⁰. In view of the fact that the counterions (X) are coordinated to the central Ni^{II} ion in the said complexes (discussion followed in the text under ir spectra), the λ_m values can be reconciled in terms of partial or total release of the anions (X) on dissolution of the solid complex in DMF.

The reflectance spectra of the nickel(II) complexes show recognisable spectral bands at 6 895–7 350, 12 050–12 345, 18 180–21 740 and 25 000–28 570 cm^{-1} . The positions of these spectral bands are quite consistent with those predicted for five-coordinate nickel(II) complexes whose structures have been established by X-ray crystallographic measurements¹¹; the bands can be assigned respectively¹² to ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3B_2$, ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E$, ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^3A_2$ and ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E$, assuming the effective symmetry to be C_{4v} . Additional bands in the uv region, viz. 31 000–35 715 and 37 040–40 000 cm^{-1} found in the reflectance spectra of the reported nickel(II) complexes can be ascribed to inter- or intra-ligand transitions.

The solution spectra of the nickel(II) species have been recorded in DMSO solutions. Each spectrum is characterised by four main bands around 8 265–9 260 (${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3B_2$), 8 850–11 110 (${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E$), 12 985–15 265 (${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^3A_2$) and 20 835–25 000 cm^{-1} (${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E$). It is pertinent to note here that for a similar set of donor atoms in a regular trigonal bipyramidal stereochemistry, only one band is expected in the near ir region at ca. 7 000 cm^{-1} , while two bands are expected for a regular square-pyramidal structure, one at 7 500 and other at 10 800 cm^{-1} (Ref. 13). Thus, the assignment of the electronic spectral bands (both d.r.s. and solution) in the reported nickel(II) complexes in an effective symmetry of C_{4v} gets tacit support and it seems reasonable to consider the structures of the present complexes as distorted square-pyramidal.

The effective magnetic moment values of the present Cu^{II} complexes are in the range 1.15–2.50 B.M. at 303 K. The molar conductance values of CuAc(MPCH)₂X (X=Cl/Br/NO₃) recorded in DMF furnish λ_m values in the range 30–35 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$; the data indicate practically non-electrolytic nature of these species with slight dissociation in DMF. The copper(II) perchlorate complex, however, shows a 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour

($\lambda_m = 96 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMF owing to release of the coordinated anion in the said solvent. The diffuse reflectance spectra of these Cu^{II} complexes exhibit spectral bands around 7 350–7 520, 18 520–21 275 and 27 025–29 410 cm^{-1} . The band at 27 000 cm^{-1} found in the bromide and nitrate complexes may be due to Cu–Cu linkage and this evidence is further supported by the magnetic moment values and the esr data of these complexes (discussed later). The solution spectra of these species show an intense broad band in the region 12 195–14 495 cm^{-1} (${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$) with a shoulder on the lower energy side at ca. 9 710–11 495 cm^{-1} (${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$), the energy level sequence ${}^3E > {}^2B_2 > {}^2A_1 > {}^2B_1$ of C_{4v} symmetry¹⁴ being assumed in the assignment of these spectral bands. The spectral data are comparable to those of five-coordinate square-pyramidal complexes of copper(II) where structures have been established by X-ray measurements¹⁵.

Esr spectra of the reported Cu^{II} complexes supplement the earlier propositions. The esr spectra of the four reported Cu^{II} complexes, CuAc(MPCH)₂X, were recorded as polycrystalline samples (esr chart was calibrated with DPPH). It has been found that none of the esr spectrum of the present Cu^{II} complexes exhibits any hyperfine structure. The esr parameters, viz. g-values were calculated using Kneubuhl's method¹⁶ and have been shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ESR PARAMETERS OF THE COPPER COMPLEX

Sl. no.	Compd.	$g_{\perp}$	$g_{\parallel}$	g_{av}	G
1.	CuAc(MPCH) ₂ Cl	2.049	2.214	2.104	4.30
2.	CuAc(MPCH) ₂ Br	2.061	2.190	2.104	3.11
3.	CuAc(MPCH) ₂ (NO ₃)	2.061	2.202	2.108	3.31
4.	CuAc(MPCH) ₂ (ClO ₄)		2.138		

The esr spectra (representative curves are shown Figs. 1 and 2) of all the Cu^{II} complexes except the Cu^{II}-perchlorate complex (Sl. no. 4, Table 2) indicate that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ and this observation is quite in good agreement with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state^{6,17}

Fig 1 ESR spectrum of CuAc(MPCH)₂Cl

Fig. 2 Esr spectrum of $\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{ClO}_4)$.

rather than a d_{z^2} state. The g_{av} values (in the 2.104–2.108 range) are compatible with five-coordinate square-pyramidal ($g=2.13$) geometry^{6,18}. In $\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Cl}$, as indicated by magnetic moment value ($\mu_B=2.2$ B.M.), there seems to be no exchange interactions between metal ions and this is also corroborated by esr spectrum of the species which gives a G value of 4.3 ($G=g_{\parallel}-2/g_{\perp}-2$), i.e. a value >4.0 (Ref. 19) reasonably suggesting no exchange interaction between Cu^{II} ions. For the complexes, $\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Br}$ and $\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{NO}_3)$, calculated G values are 3.11 and 3.31 respectively. These observations point out the presence of exchange interactions between Cu^{II} ions which has been reflected in the subnormal magnetic moment values ($\mu_B=1.58$ and 1.15 B.M. respectively) of these complexes. The esr spectrum of $\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{ClO}_4)$ is isotropic with a g -value of 2.138.

Ir spectra: The uncomplexed ligand, $\text{AcH}(\text{MPCH})_2$ (the isolated variety) shows a strong spectral band in the 3μ region, i.e. at 3200 (b, s) cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the hydrogen bonded N–H stretching frequency². The moderately strong bands appearing at 1680 , 1570 , 860 and 680 cm^{-1} can be attributed²⁰ respectively to the amide-I ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$), azomethine $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ of the hydrazone residue (of the ligand) and the in-plane deformation of the pyrazole ring. The bands at 1550 and 1470 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the pyrazole ring²⁰. Thus, the ir data of the solid ligand (isolated in small amount) clearly show that the desired macrocycle, acetylacetonate bis(methylpyrazole carbohydrazone) is formed and characterised. With the presumption that the ligand, $\text{AcH}(\text{MPCH})_2$ is formed in situ, the ir spectra of the metal complexes when compared to the stretching frequencies of the solid free ligand, the characteristic spectral changes can be successfully utilised to have an insight the mode of linkage of the ligand molecule to the central metal ion.

A positive shift ($\Delta\nu=30-50$ cm^{-1}) in the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine) in the spectra of all the metal complexes indicates involvement of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination. Such an increase in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$

on complexation has been interpreted by earlier workers²¹ in terms of electron repelling character of the $-\text{CH}_3$ groups attached to azomethine carbon atom of the ligand.

Simultaneous positive shifts in the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ ($\Delta\nu=10-50$ cm^{-1}) of the pyrazole ring in these complexes compared to those in the free ligand suggest²² that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring takes part in the coordination to the central metal ion.

The far-ir spectral data (Table 3) show non-ligands bands in the regions $230-255$ and $460-480$ cm^{-1} which can safely be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (pyrazole)²³ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (azomethine)²⁴ respectively.

TABLE 3—FAR-IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (pyrazole)	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (azomethine)
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Cl}]$	240	460
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Br}]$	250	460
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{NO}_3)]$	240	465
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{SCN})]$	250	460
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{ClO}_4)]$	245	465
$[\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{BF}_4)]$	255	480
$[\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Cl}]$	240	480
$[\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{Br}]$	230	465
$[\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{NO}_3)]$	245	485
$[\text{CuAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{C.O.})]$	250	465

The spectra of the halo complexes show metal-halogen stretching frequencies in the regions $275-280$ and $220-240$ cm^{-1} differentiable from $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (ring) which may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Br}}$ respectively²⁵.

The ir spectra of the nitrate complexes, $\text{MAc}(\text{MPCH})_2\text{X}$, where $\text{M}=\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{X}=\text{NO}_3$, show bands at 1380 , 1350 and 810 cm^{-1} , assignable to components of ν_3 and ν_2 respectively. The data indicate the monodentate nature of the nitrate ion²⁶. Appearance of new bands at 230 and 225 cm^{-1} can be assigned to ν_{NiONO_2} and ν_{CuONO_2} vibrations respectively²⁷. In the ir spectra of the perchlorate complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II), the components of $\nu_{\text{Cl-O}}$ in C_{2v} symmetry have been found around $1110-1160$, $1090-1115$ and $1025-1030$ cm^{-1} which indicate clearly the monodentate nature of perchlorate ion²⁸. The ir spectrum of the thiocyanate complex of nickel(II), $\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{NCS})$, exhibits two bands at 2105 and 785 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ stretching indicating the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate group²⁹ in that complex. In the far-ir spectrum, a band appears at 520 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to δ_{NCS} mode of vibrations of N-bonded thiocyanate³⁰ group. The complex also shows new band at 280 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{Ni-NCS}}$ ³¹.

The fluoborate complex of nickel(II), $\text{NiAc}(\text{MPCH})_2(\text{BF}_4)$ shows splitting of the ν_3 mode of vibration of BF_4 ion into components appearing at 1130 , 1070 and 1055 cm^{-1} which suggests the presence of a monodentate fluoborate in C_{2v} symmetry³².

In the light of the recorded experimental data on the reported nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes and their possible interpretations as discussed above, it may be reasonably inferred that the macrocyclic primary ligand molecule $\text{AcH}(\text{MPCH})_2$ (formed in situ) exhibits a neutral tetradentate function, coordinating through two pyrazolyl (ring) nitrogens and two azomethine ($-\text{C}=\text{N}$) nitrogens with the counterion (X) being coordinated to the central metal atom. Based on analytical, magnetic, electronic, esr and ir spectral data, the following 5-coordinate square-pyramidal configuration (Fig. 3) seems quite probable; however, absence of single crystal X -ray data for any of these species such a proposition for structure of the complex is highly conjectural.

Fig. 3

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. quality. Metal(II) bromide, perchlorate and fluoborate were prepared from metal(II) carbonate and the appropriate acids and were used after recrystallisation. Spectrograde solvents were used for spectral and conductance measurements.

Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of acetylaceton-bis-methylpyrazolyl carbohydrazone, $\text{AcH}(\text{MPCH})_2$:

Although the desired Schiff base, $\text{AcH}(\text{MPCH})_2$ was successfully synthesised by the condensation of 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carbohydrazide² (MPCH) and acetylaceton (AcacH) and its purity was checked by C, H, N analyses, but because of extremely poor yield (~10%) and low solubility of the product, the reported metal complexes were synthesised by a template methodology as described below.

NiAc(MPCH)₂X (X=Cl, Br, NO₃, ClO₄, BF₄): A solution of MPCH (0.01 mol, 1.4 g) in dry methanol (20 ml) was refluxed with acetylaceton (0.005 mol, 0.5 ml) for 1 h at water-bath temperature. The resultant solution (presumably the Schiff base formed in situ) was then mixed with a dry methanolic solution (20 ml) of anhydrous nickel(II) salts, NiX_2 (X=Cl, Br, NO₃, ClO₄, BF₄; 0.01 mol) and

further refluxed for 16 h. The green solution obtained was concentrated almost to dryness and the green mass left was extracted with dry chloroform. Usually the CHCl_3 -extract on removal of the solvent produced the desired complex. In the cases of the nickel(II) nitrate and fluoborate species, cold ethanol/cold acetone was used for the precipitation of the desired complex.

NiAc(MPCH)₂(SCN): An ethanolic solution of nickel(II) thiocyanate (generated by mixing 0.01 mol of Ni^{II} nitrate with 0.02 mol of potassium isothiocyanate and filtering off the precipitated KNO_3) was run into a hot dry ethanolic (previously refluxed) solution of MPCH (0.01 mol) and acetylaceton (0.005 mol). The resultant mixture was worked out as described above to have the desired complex species after extraction with cold acetone.

CuAc(MPCH)₂X (X=Cl, Br, NO₃, ClO₄): To a solution of MPCH (0.01 mol, 1.4 g) in dry methanol (20 ml), acetylaceton (0.005 mol, 0.5 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h at water-bath temperature. It was then mixed with a solution of anhydrous copper(II) salts CuX_2 (0.01 mol) in dry MeOH (20 ml) and refluxed again for 2 h. The green solution obtained was concentrated on a water-bath and cooled. Microcrystalline green compounds of various shades were found to be precipitated with time. The compound, in each case, was collected as usual after washing with ice-cold methanol and dried.

All the reported Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of acetylaceton-bis-methylpyrazolyl carbohydrazones were found insoluble in water and other organic solvents such as low molecular weight alcohols, benzene and chloroform. They are, however, soluble in donor solvents like DMF and DMSO.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content were determined in a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyser or in a Thomas 35 CH analyser. The metal contents were estimated by conventional gravimetric methods, viz. nickel as nickel dimethylglyoximate and copper as $\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2 \cdot \text{HgI}_4$ after decomposing the metal complex by acid mixture.

The magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature were determined by Gouy's method using $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$ ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs at 293 K) as calibrant. The molar conductances of the complexes were recorded in DMF by using a Systronic 303 conductivity bridge. The electronic diffuse reflectance spectra were measured on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer (RSIC, IIT, Madras). The solution spectra (DMSO) on a Cary 17D spectrophotometer (RSIC, Bose Institute, Calcutta), ir spectra (CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 559B spectrophotometer and esr spectra of on a E112 spectrometer.

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